

**The cognitive processing of EFL readers completing banked gap-fill tasks:
Evidence from eye-tracking**

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The present study aimed to explore whether different levels of reading proficiency and task difficulty influence specific eye-movement metrics and how these relate to higher- and lower-level reading processes. A mixed-methods design was employed with twenty university students who completed two banked gap-fill tasks across B1 and C1 levels. Quantitative data from eye-tracking measures were complemented by stimulated recall interviews to gain deeper insights into participants' cognitive strategies, including inference and background knowledge utilization. The findings showed that, at lower level (B1), there are no significant differences in eye-movement patterns between high- and low-performing readers, suggesting the tasks mainly assess local, lower-level decoding skills. At the advanced C1 level, slight differences emerge, with higher performers demonstrating more efficient processing and greater reliance on higher-level reading cognitive processes. Regression analysis revealed that lower performers tend to switch their gaze more frequently between the text and word bank, indicating reliance on lower-level processes. The qualitative data supported these findings, showing that higher performers engaged more frequently in inference and background knowledge, particularly at the C1 level. The study highlights the utility of eye-tracking as a valid tool to examine real-time cognitive processing and its implications for test design and language teaching. Recommendations include employing higher-level reading tasks for assessing global reading skills and integrating eye-movement analysis into test validation processes.

Keywords: Eye-tracking; Banked gap-filling Readings; Reading Cognitive Processes

1. Introduction

Reading comprehension is considered as a basis of academic skill and prerequisite to professional proficiency. It impacts knowledge acquisition,

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critical thinking, and effective communication across different fields (Grabe & Stoller, 2011; Salmani Nodoushan, 2003). It is commonly believed that interest in second language reading research has probably increased in the past 15 years. Part of this interest is perhaps the result of the increasing recognition that reading abilities are vital for academic learning (Salmani Nodoushan, 2020; Schmitt, 2010). An important related area of reading which has recently received research attention is readers' cognitive processes. Understanding L2 reading cognitive processes can contribute to the knowledge about what the construct of L2 reading itself presents, what cognitive processing skills are involved in comprehending a text, what features can make a distinction between proficient and less proficient readers, how readers' strengths and weaknesses can be identified, and what instructional remedies can be suggested (Alderson, 2000; Grabe & Stoller, 2011). Needless to say, test-takers use different cognitive processes including lexical access, syntactic parsing, semantic interpretation, and inferencing when engaged in reading comprehension tasks (Kintsch, 1998; Rayner, 2009). To the best of the researchers' knowledge, different studies have been conducted to analyze the cognitive processes applied by readers. Accordingly, cognitive theories of reading have been presented to explain what psychological or mental processes readers use to comprehend a text (Graesser et al., 1997; McNamara & Magliano, 2009). Among those theories, Khalifa and Weir's (2009) model has paid close attention to the role of readers' cognitive operations (Bax, 2013).

The current study employed the central processing core of Khalifa and Weir's (2009) cognitive model of reading (as cited in Brunfaut & McCray, 2015) as a framework for analyzing the cognitive processes engaged by participants of the current study. According to Brunfaut and McCray (2015), the model has three components: metacognitive, central processing core, and knowledge base. Khalifa and Weir (2009) have listed the cognitive processes in reading in the central processing core of their model (from lower to higher level). The lower-level processes include word recognition, lexical access, syntactic parsing, and establishing propositional meaning. The higher level processes comprise inferencing, building a mental model, and creating a text level or intertextual representation (Khalifa & Weir, 2009, as cited in Brunfaut & McCray, 2015).

While until recently different studies have analyzed the cognitive processes used by readers while completing different reading types (e.g., Bax & Weir, 2012; Bax, 2013; Brunfaut & McCray, 2015), few studies have investigated what psychological or mental processes readers use to comprehend banked gap-filling items (e.g., Gao & Gu, 2008; Sasaki, 2000; Yamashita, 2003), and more importantly, the construct of banked gap-filling readings has remained relatively under-investigated specifically in the context of Iran.

Brown (2003) believes that the employment of higher-level reading processes when completing banked gap-fill items might depend on the level of the test-takers' performance. To be more specific, Brown believes that test-takers with lower English proficiency cannot handle more complex information and apply lower-level reading processes, while test-takers with higher English proficiency have the linguistic ability to take advantage of more global textual information. However, a few studies have investigated the extent to which Brown's hypothesis applies to the banked gap-fill items (e.g., McCray & Brunfaut, 2018; Yamashita, 2003).

The studies mentioned hitherto have investigated the construct of gap filling-items by analyzing the cognitive processes utilized by test-takers while comprehending the tasks. In order to generate data on cognitive processes, the researchers have applied a common technique called verbal protocol—also known as think-aloud protocol. To be more specific, test-takers were supposed to describe aloud all their thoughts and ideas during their performance of a given cognitive task. Although a number of studies have used such a measure to investigate the construct of gap-filling items (e.g., Gao & Gu, 2008; Sasaki, 2000; Yamashita, 2003), little research has employed an eye-tracker to illuminate the processes that take place during task performance to investigate the construct of gap-filling items (e.g., McCray & Brunfaut, 2018). In addition, each of these previous studies has been conducted in the context of English as a first language, and only a few researchers have tried a wider look on the topic and investigated the gap-filling items in the domain of second language reading. More importantly, fewer studies carried out in the domain of English as a foreign language, and to the best of the researchers' knowledge, no studies have so far investigated the construct of banked gap-filling items in Iran. Thus, the aim of the current study is to investigate the construct of banked gap-fill items by analyzing the cognitive processes of reading utilized by test-takers while comprehending the task via an eye-tracker. More specifically, the present study examined the types of processing applied by higher and lower performing participants to delineate precisely the construct being measured.

2. Background

2.1. Banked gap-filling reading

Banked gap-filling tests belong to a family of test types called 'gap-fill'—also known as 'cloze'. A gap filling test contains tasks which are made up of a text from which a number of words have been deleted, and the test-takers are challenged to restore the omitted words (Davies et al., 1999; Salmani Nodoushan, 2007). In gap-filling tasks the test takers are required to place a word into a blank space in the text which has been omitted by the test developer. In some cases, the test takers are supposed to complete the text by

choosing a word from a number of different options which are provided for each and every gap.

As an alternative, test takers are required to generate lexical items in order to fill the gaps. This type of the gap-filling is called open-gap filling (Alderson & Cseresznyés, 2003). In a different type of gap-filling tasks—i.e., banked gap filling—the words which are deleted from the text are provided, but randomly ordered in a ‘bank’ outside of the text, mostly with some additional words as distractors. For each gap in the text, the test-takers need to choose a word from the bank to reconstruct the passage (Alderson & Cseresznyés, 2003). This type of the gap-filling is called banked gap-filling. Banked gap-fill tasks are often used as part of reading tests—e.g., in the Aptis test by British Council (n.d.) or PTE by Academic test (Pearson, n.d.). However, it is surprising that it is not clear that exactly what is being measured by banked gap-filling tasks (McCray & Brunfaut, 2018).

Nevertheless, a few studies have investigated the construct of gap-filling items by analyzing the cognitive processes test-takers utilize to complete the tasks. Sasaki (2000) conducted a study on gap-filling. He investigated the effect of cultural familiarity on a cloze task. To do so, only one text was applied, but Sasaki (2000) replaced a number of words to create a culturally familiar adaptation of the same text. Immediate retrospections by 60 Japanese learners of English showed that test-takers who responded to the culturally familiar text employed more within-sentence and within-clause information than those who completed the unfamiliar text.

Another study regarding test-takers' cognitive process on open gap-fill items was conducted by Yamashita (2003). He found some evidence in support of a related study done on Brown's (2003) hypothesis. Although her sample size was small, Yamashita (2003) compared the concurrent verbal protocols of six less-skilled with six skilled Japanese readers on a 16-item gap-fill task. The study concluded that less skilled readers reported more emphasis on local grammatical information while more skilled readers tended to apply local information in the text more to confirm their answers which they had already established through more global reading.

A process-oriented study investigating banked gap-fill tasks is by Gao and Gu (2008). They conducted a process-oriented research to investigate a banked gap-fill task. They revealed the process of task completion of three groups (high, medium, and low) of Chinese English learners based on CET-4 reading scores on a 10-item banked gap-fill task. Verbal protocol data were generated from the study. The findings showed that the most common response strategy was to refer to local information as opposed to sentential, textual or inter-textual information.

The above-mentioned studies used verbal protocol to generate data on cognitive processes. As Yamashita (2003) observed, when responses to gap-filling tasks were automatized in readers, the verbal reports data were not able to provide processing information. In other words, Yamashita doubted the extent to which verbal reports could explain information about test-takers' lower-level reading cognitive processing. Therefore, it is perhaps clear that only partial information has been obtained in these studies. Eye-tracking is considered as a possible way to collect data on the cognitive processing during reading which does not rely on the perception and recall of processes.

2.2. Eye-tracking and reading cognitive processes

The area of research on first language (L1) reading is huge. In the context of second/foreign language (L2) reading, however, a great deal of research is yet needed to figure out the cognitive processes involved in text comprehension. Multiple cognitive theories of reading have been proposed to explain what cognitive processes are used by the readers in order to comprehend a text (Graesser et al., 1997; McNamara, & Magliano, 2009).

It should be mentioned that text understanding is brought about by the interaction of both bottom-up and top-down processes (McNamara, & Magliano, 2009; Verhoeven & Perfetti, 2008). Bottom-up or lower-level processes, such as decoding lexical items or understanding propositions at the level of the sentence, are considered automatic and use extremely small amount of cognitive resources. The processes in lower-level are understood through text-based inferences. At this level, the phases of comprehension where the main meaning connections between the propositions are established are made (Kintsch & Rawson, 2005; Perfetti, 2007; Zwaan & Singer, 2003). Conversely, in top-down or higher-level processes, much more cognitive effort is utilized. Readers' background information and knowledge are used to enrich the understanding of the text (Graesser et al., 1994; Zwaan & Brown, 1996).

Verbal protocol is a common technique in cognitive psychology in order to study cognitive processes (van den Broek et al., 2001). A verbal protocol is an introspective method in which the readers are asked to describe aloud all their thoughts and ideas while completing a given cognitive task (Sternberg & Sternberg, 2012). To be more specific, when readers are thinking aloud while performing a cognitive task, it is called concurrent verbal protocol—also known as think aloud protocol. When the description of how the task is solved, is reported after accomplishing the activity itself, it is called retrospective verbal protocol (Ericsson, 1988; Ericsson & Simon, 1993; Taylor & Dionne, 2000).

Therefore, verbal reports have been increasingly used as data to analyze the reading cognitive processes applied by test-takers to complete a given task (cf. Gau & Gu, 2008; Sasaki, 2000; Pressley & Afllerbach, 1995; Yamashita, 2003). On the other hand, verbal protocols have been criticized in that they risk reactivity and veridicality (Bowles, 2010). Reactivity deals with the intrusiveness of thought verbalization with the undesirable result of disrupting the cognitive and thinking processes whereas veridicality relates to whether verbal protocol can accurately reflect the problem solver's cognitive processes (Ericsson, 1988). In addition, since some reading cognitive processes are unconscious and automatic, it is believed that not all thought sequences can be reported (Ericsson & Simon, 1993). One possible way to enrich data on the cognitive processing during reading which does not rely on the recall of processes is via eye-tracking. Furthermore, Brunfaut and McCray (2015) observed that eye-tracking gave more insights into lower-level cognitive processing than did a verbal protocol method. For these reasons, using eye tracking as a data collection technique is needed. In response to this call for data collection, the present study took advantage of the eye-tracker as a data collector.

Eye-tracking is a useful tool which allows for the moment-by-moment scrutiny of processing decisions made by the participants during natural and uninterrupted comprehension (Godfroid et al., 2015; Rayner, 1998, 2009). Although eye-tracking is a new method in the field of language testing, it sounds quite valuable as a data collection tool due to the minimal cognitive disruption of the test-taking process, since test-takers complete the tasks as they would normally (McCray & Brunfaut, 2018). The use of eye-tracking in reading research is predicated on the assumption that there is a close link between the point in a text on which the readers' eyes fixate and the focus of readers' attention at that moment (Rayner, 1998). Eye movements which can be recorded from eye-tracking are considered as a proper data source to record participants' covert attentional processing. They allow researchers to examine what is happening during real-time processing by providing fixations, saccades, regressions, and eye gaze. Fixation is the time during which eyes remain stationary. Saccades are rapid eye movements from one fixation point to another. And regressions are eye movements from right to left (Godfroid & Uggen, 2013).

2.3. Eye-track research studies

Bax (2013) made use of an eye tracker to investigate test takers' cognitive processing while completing onscreen *IELTS*. The study focused on differences in reading behaviors of successful and unsuccessful candidates while completing *IELTS* test items. The participants were a group of Malaysian undergraduates ($N = 71$). They took an onscreen test consisting of two *IELTS*

reading passages with 11 test items. Eye movements of a random sample of these participants ($n = 38$) were tracked. Findings revealed significant differences between successful and unsuccessful test takers on a number of dimensions, including their ability to read expeditiously and their focus on particular aspects of the test items and texts while no observable difference was noted in other items.

In another study, to the best of our knowledge close to the present study, McCray and Brunfaut (2018) employed an eye-tracker to generate data on cognitive processing in reading. The participants were combination of L2 learners and native speakers of English. Their study investigated test-takers' processing while completing banked gap-fill tasks. It was designed to test reading proficiency to tap theoretically based expectations about the variation in cognitive processes of test-takers across levels of performance. Twenty-eight test-takers' eye traces on 24 banked gap-fill items were analyzed according to seven online eye-tracking measures representing overall, text, and task processing. The findings demonstrated that the application of eye-tracking can give some insights into cognitive processing while completing banked gap-fill tasks.

Needless to say, most of the studies applying eye-tracker as data generator related to cognitive process engaged by test takers in reading, examined native English speakers in what has been termed the 'default' mode of reading—that is, when comprehension is proceeding without difficulty, and the eyes are continuing to move forward along a line of text (Reichle et al., 2009) with relatively few regressions. In contrast, much eye movement behavior on the part of second language (L2) readers during reading tests is significantly different from this—for example, when a reader reads a test item first then searches for relevant parts of a text (Bax, 2013). Furthermore, to the best of our knowledge, no studies have applied an eye-tracker so far to investigate the cognitive processes test-takers take while completing reading comprehension, especially banked gap-fill items in EFL context. More specifically, such studies have not gone under study in Iran to see if the findings are in the line with studies in the contexts of ESL and L1. Therefore, the current study is guided by the following research questions:

- 1) Is there any significant difference between the eye-movements of higher-performing test-takers and lower-performing test-takers in terms of saccades and regressions in B1 and C1?
- 2) Is there any significant difference between the higher-performing test-takers and lower-performing test-takers in terms of their cognitive processing while completing banked gap-filling items in two different levels of reading B1 and C1 as evidence from eye-movement data?

3. Method

The present study employed a mixed-methods research design, including both quantitative and qualitative approaches in order to investigate reading cognitive processes applied by the test-takers to complete the banked gap-filling tasks in the EFL context in Iran. To analyze the eye-tracking data including fixations, regressions, and saccades which were collected from the participants while they completed the banked gap-filling reading tasks, Independent Samples t-tests were run in order to compare the mean scores between the two groups of high performance readers and low performance readers across the three levels of banked gap-filling readings (B1 and C1). In addition to the quantitative analysis, a qualitative approach was also adopted by the researchers. After completing the banked gap-filling reading tasks, the participants were individually asked to verbalize what they had done and gone through in doing the tasks. By integrating both quantitative and qualitative methods, the current study aimed to provide a comprehensive analysis of the cognitive processes which were engaged by the participants of the study in the context of EFL.

3.1. Participants

The participants of the study were 20 university students majoring in different fields of science at Ferdowsi University of Mashhad. Fourteen of them were studying in master's program while six were undergraduate students. In order to include them as the participants of the present study, they were needed to share a couple of common characteristics. Initially, all the participants had attempted the Academic module of the *IELTS* test in the past year. Secondly, they all fell into the age range of 20 to 35. Finally, they were all native speakers of Farsi. Therefore, English is considered a foreign language for them.

Since, one of the main components of the present study is the linguistic proficiency of the participants, the differentiation criterion was their *IELTS* scores. According to *IELTS* website/*IELTS* in CEFR scale, the minimum score for being an independent English user is 4, and the minimum score for being a proficient English user is 7. Since the current research focused on the reading skill, the participants' reading scores on academic *IELTS* were taken into account. Reading scores of 4 to 6.5 (based on the *IELTS* website/*IELTS* in CEFR scale) show the lower-performing test-taker category (B1, B2) to which 10 participants belonged while the reading scores of 7 to 8 (C1) mark higher-performing test-taker group which covered the remaining 10 participants.

3.2. Instrumentation

The eye-track has been introduced in two famous brands: Swedish brand of Tobii and German brand of SMI. The researchers used the SMI ETG-2 of

Psychological-behavioral Laboratory at Sport Science Faculty at Ferdowsi University of Mashhad. In order to record and register where the eyes were looking at while the test-takers were completing the gap-filling reading tasks and obtaining the participants' eye patterns, saccades, regressions, and fixation, the SMI ETG-2 Eye tracker device was employed. The device is made in Germany, and is designed with binocular technology; it sends an infrared beam of light to one's eyes and receives its reflection. It also calculates the angle of the eye against the face. The eye tracker displays the image captured by the front-facing camera in I-view software. After recording the information by its camera in the first step, it visualizes the qualitative data and converts it to quantitative data using BeGaze software.

The participants' eye-movement data including saccades, regressions, and fixation was collected on three banked gap-fill tasks. The researchers employed PET Masterclass by Oxford University Press for B1 and The Gold C1 advanced Exam Maximiser New Edition by Pearson for C1. The tasks from the first banked gap fill task contains a reading paragraph in B1 level with 8 gaps with 8 suggested words in its bank, and the second reading in C1 level provided with 8 gaps and 8 words in its bank. The three banked gap fill tasks enjoyed three different topics

Some eye tracker devices analyze data automatically, but the SMI ETG-2 eye tracker implemented in the current study, in spite of being high-tech, did not provide data itself so that the researcher did initial analysis manually. In order to analyze the collected data obtained from the eye track device and explore any possible significant differences among the variables of reading cognitive processes, the test-takers' performance level and the CEFR level of reading tasks (B1 and C1), four hypotheses were formulated. It should be noted that these hypotheses were constructed in light of Khalifa and Weir's (2009) reading cognitive model as cited in McCray & Brunfaut (2015). Additionally, three general eye track metrics (i.e., fixations, saccade, and regression) were employed to test the hypotheses in the current study. Three types of processes were tapped:

- Overall processing: the way test-takers complete the text as a whole (text and word bank)
- Text processing: engaging the main text without reference to the word bank
- Task processing: engaging interactions between the text and the word bank

Though eye-tracking is precise enough to explore and investigate test-takers' lower-levels reading cognitive processing, it is unlikely to give insight into higher-level reading cognitive processing such as inferences engaged by the test-takers (Brunfaut & McCray, 2015). Therefore, the researchers did the

stimulated recall interviews in order to generate more insights into higher-level reading cognitive process. To be more specific, the researchers aimed at investigating to what extent the participants' background knowledge, guessing, and inferencing cognitive processes are taken into account by test-takers while completing gap filling tasks at three different reading levels.

3.3. Procedure

To collect the data, the current study had two substantial stages. In the first stage, the researcher needed to arrange meetings with participants and the eye-track operator individually. Prior to the experimental task, the participants received an email describing the purpose and the method of data collection. Moreover, in each email the exact attendance time of each individual was specified based on their suggested available free time. Since the presence time for all twenty participants was scheduled for five days, the operator typically administered the task to about four or five participants every day. Typically, each participant was shown a two-minute video displaying how to work with the eye-tracker device in order to get familiar with the device. Answers for any possible questions related to the eye-tracker device for any participant were provided by the operator. At first, each participant sat in front of a 22-inch monitor equipped with the eye-tracking device and the eye-tracker operator explained the rubrics of using the device. He invited the participants not to move their heads during calibration and only follow the red spots on the screen by their eyes; during the reading task they had to move their head in the direction of their eyes. Then the operator calibrated the eye track device via the glasses of the eye tracker for each participant individually in order to detect the participant's eyes correctly. After that, three reading tasks appeared on the screen consecutively. The first reading passage was in B1 level. For the respondents' convenience each blank was marked with a number and the test taker was supposed to match the numbers with the appropriate words from the bank. Without any break or pause the same process was repeated for reading task 2 (C1 level).

After each participant successfully implemented three reading tasks, the second stage called the 'interview' began. The second phase was conducted after the administration of eye tracking device in order to collect verbal data. To be more specific, each participant was supposed to undergo stimulated recall interview. To this end, when the participants completed the tasks, the replay of their eye-movements was played for each reading, they were asked to verbalize how they had approached the reading tasks and what they were thinking during the tasks completion. Their oral responses were then recorded and transcribed by the researchers. After that, the transcriptions were imported into the qualitative data analysis software *Maxqda* for coding and analysis. The coding categories included inferencing, background knowledge,

and pure guess (cf. Brunfaut & McCray, 2015). It is worth mentioning that the participants were also asked to verbalize if they had taken the advantages of using the mentioned codes in order to attempt to complete the task. After coding, the data were analyzed using the software. In order to enable the participants to verbalize and express their thoughts with ease, the recall interviews were conducted in the participants' first language—Farsi.

4. Results

The first research question investigated if there is any significant difference between the eye-movements of lower-performing test-takers and higher-performing test-takers in terms of saccades and regressions in B1 and C1. The mean scores of regressions employed by low performers and high performers were analyzed for the main texts. The mean scores in B1 are ($M = 36.20, SD = 7.540$) and ($M = 26.00, SD = 3.432$) respectively. Also, ($M = 34.60, SD = 7.545$) and ($M = 27.10, SD = 5.587$) are the mean scores of regressions for both groups for C1 level. To answer the first research question, the researcher ran an Independent Samples *t*-Test. a significant difference between the high performers and low performers on regressions of main text was only observed in B1: $t = 3.894, p = .001, df = 18$. In level C1 the results showed a slightly significant difference between the performance of high test-takers and low test-takers on regressions of main text: $t = 2.526, p = .021, df = 18$. The mean scores of saccades which were collected from both high and low performers in B1 level are ($M = 562.40, SD = 84.136$) and ($M = 584.80, SD = 94.012$), respectively, and also for C1, the means scores of saccades for both high and low performers are ($M = 670.00, SD = 98.774$) and ($M = 733.10, SD = 97.354$), respectively. The results show that a significant difference between the high performers and low performers on saccade was not observed in B1: $t = 0.561, p = .581, df = 18$. In level C1, the results showed no significant difference as well between the performance of high test-takers and low test-takers on saccade: $t = 1.439, p = .167, df = 18$. Relying on the data, there is no significant difference between the eye-movements of higher-performing test-takers and lower-performing test-takers in terms of saccades and regressions in B1 and C1 and only there was a significant difference between the two groups in term of regressions in B1.

In order to answer the second research question, the researcher developed four hypotheses. The first hypothesis (H1) posits that higher-performing test-takers complete the gap filling reading task in less time than the lower performing test-takers; in other words, high performers are able to do the same cognitive work needed to resolve the gaps in less time. This hypothesis is based on Khalifa and Weir's (2009) model which hypothesized that in higher-performing test-takers' word recognition happens with a faster pace, which consequently leads to more cognitive capacity to be directed towards higher-

level reading cognitive process needed to decide which word fits the gap (McCray & Brunfaut, 2018). In order to test the first hypothesis, the mean scores of overall fixations of higher performers ($M = 108213.20$, $SD = 18860.588$) and lower performers ($M = 114435.90$, $SD = 9166.343$) in B1 were analyzed. To compare the means, the researchers conducted an Independent Samples t -Test: $t = .938$, $p = .360$, $df = 18$. Accordingly, the first hypothesis was rejected.

The second hypothesis (H2) argues that higher performers spend less time focusing on the main text of the task compared to the lower performers. The underlying fact to discuss the obtained result is that higher performers seem to engage additional cognitive resources to spend on higher-level, more global processing engendered by the sequences of words in the task's text contrary to local, lower-level processing—that is recognition of the word and lexical processing (McCray & Brunfaut, 2018). In order to test the second hypothesis, the mean scores of fixations of the main text of higher performers ($M = 67507.50$, $SD = 11297.108$) and lower performers ($M = 66024.70$, $SD = 8247.991$) in B1 were analyzed. To compare the means, the researchers ran an Independent Samples t -Test: $t = .335$, $p = .741$, $df = 18$. Accordingly, the second hypothesis (H2) was also rejected.

The third hypothesis (H3) posits that higher-performing test-takers need less time to focus on the word bank compared to lower performing test-takers. This is because, not a remarkable capacity of higher-performers' cognition ability would be required to decode the words in the word bank (McCray & Brunfaut, 2018). In order to explore the third hypothesis, the mean scores of fixations on bank of higher performers ($M = 40704.65$, $SD = 8946.622$) and lower performers ($M = 48411.10$, $SD = 8172.683$) in B1 were analyzed. Independent Samples t -Test results showed that significant difference between the high performers and low performers on fixations of bank in B1 was not observed: $t = .2011$, $p = .060$, $df = 18$. Therefore, the third hypothesis (H3) could not be accepted.

The fourth hypothesis (H4) claims that higher-performing test-takers switch their gaze less between the word bank and the main text compared to lower performing test-takers. This is because it raises the argument that with higher levels of cognitive capacity, the higher performers can better retain the word-bank list in the in their working memory. This urges less need to switch between the text and the word bank to refresh one's working memory for the purpose of completing the gaps whereas the opposite may be the case for the lower performers who may switch more (McCray & Brunfaut, 2018). The mean scores of regressions to the bank which were collected from both high ($M = 26.60$, $SD = 2.989$) and low performers ($M = 35.70$, $SD = 7.573$) at B1 level were

input to an Independent Samples *t*-Test ($t = .3.535, p = .002, df = 18$), and the fourth hypothesis (H4) was accepted.

As for the C1 level of reading, the same hypotheses were tested. In order to test the first hypothesis (H1), the mean scores of overall fixations of higher performers ($M = 122449.00, SD = 24579.938$) and lower performers ($M = 173364.60, SD = 23487.877.233$) in C1 were submitted to an Independent Samples *t*-Test ($t = 2.868, p = .010, df = 18$), and the first hypothesis could be accepted. As for the second hypothesis, high ($M = 74782.50, SD = 15858.803$) and low performers ($M = 95648.88, SD = 16421.623$) at C1 level showed a significant difference ($t = 2.890, p = .010, df = 18$), and the second hypothesis (H2) was accepted. The third hypothesis (H3) concerning higher performers ($M = 47693.40, SD = 15864.161$) and lower performers ($M = 60638.75, SD = 11508.914$) at C1 level was rejected based on the Independent Samples *t*-Test results: $t = 2.089, p = .051, df = 18$. Finally, the fourth hypothesis (H4) was accepted since the mean of the high ($M = 26.50, SD = 5.442$) and low ($M = 34.50, SD = 7.517$) performers at C1 level showed significant differences ($t = 2.726, p = .014, df = 18$).

Stimulated recall interviews initially mirror the numerical data obtained by eye-tracking device. To be more specific, the participants' verbal explanations of what they have done are in line with the data collected by tracking the eye movements of the participants in completing the banked gap-filling tasks. The findings from Maxqda are presented as follows:

- Guessing was the most common strategy to complete the banked gap-filling tasks when the participants were unable to use their linguistic knowledge for the task completion. This strategy was more evident in low performance test-takers. In details, in B1 no participants in either groups used the guessing strategy to complete the tasks. At C1 level the frequency of guessing was 10 times for the low performers while it happened only 7 times for high performance test-takers.
- Inference was another key point in participants' interviews that took the second rank in the amount of frequency. In short, no participant took the advantage of this strategy at B1. At C1 level, however, the frequency of inferencing was 7 times for the high-performance test-takers. They reported that this strategy was effective in banked gap-filling task while no low-performance participants put this strategy into practice.
- Background knowledge was not engaged by participants in either groups at B1. At C1 level, low performer participants did not use their background knowledge to complete the task whereas high performer participants took the record of 6 times to apply this strategy in order to complete the task.

Based on the interviews, high performance test-takers applied high reading cognitive processes in completing gap-filling readings tasks only at C1 level whereas low performance test-takers did not favor high reading cognitive processes in completing gap-filling tasks at C1 level.

5. Discussion

The findings of the study mentioned above indicate that employing an eye-tracking device can provide researchers with valuable insights into reading cognitive processes involved in completing banked gap-fill tasks. Moreover, this technology reveals the differences of reading cognitive processing engaged by higher- and lower-performance test takers. Our findings lend support to the efficiency of this tool as supported by the findings of studies carried out by Bax (2013), Bax and Weir (2012), and Brunfaut and McCray (2015).

For the first research question, the researcher observed a significant difference between higher performance test-takers, and lower performance test-takers in terms of regressions only at B1 and C1 levels of readings. The findings are in line with the study carried out by Holmqvist et al., (2011). They argued that as the ability in reading comprehension increases, the number of regressions decreases. This indicates that test-takers with higher performance have fewer problems with word recognition and lexical access which are the lower-level reading cognitive process (Brunfaut & McCray, 2015). Based on Brunfaut and McCray 2015, as the ability of high performers increases, the number of saccades decreases, and this also indicates the increased processing efficiency of higher performance test-takers. The results of their study showed there was no significant difference between the two groups of participants, and the findings of the present study also led to the same results in Iranian EFL contexts.

The analysis of relevant data for the first hypothesis revealed that there was no significant difference between the two groups of participants at B1 level in applying different levels of reading cognitive processes. More precisely, the findings indicated that it could not be claimed that higher performance test-takers will apply different levels of reading cognitive processes compared to the lower performance test-takers. The findings are contrary to the expectations of the study which was conducted by McCray and Brunfaut (2018). The mentioned hypothesis claims that higher-performing test-takers' word recognition happens at a faster pace, which consequently leads to more cognitive capacity to be directed towards higher-level reading cognitive processes needed to decide which word fits the gap.

Interestingly, the hypothesis was accepted at C1 level which shows when the level of reading increases, there can be differences between higher performance test-takers and lower performance test-takers in terms of

applying reading cognitive process. To be more specific, when test-takers deal with a difficult reading, the higher test-takers may apply more high-level reading cognitive processes compared to lower-level test-takers.

For the second (H2) and third hypotheses (H3) of the study dealing with the time that test-takers spend on the main text and the bank of options, no significant difference was observed in either of the two levels of reading. There was only a slightly significant difference at C1 level regarding the point that higher performance test-takers spend less time on the main text compared to the lower performance test-takers. Due to the fact that the mean scores of higher performance test-takers and lower performance test-takers were not significantly different, the conclusion that the two groups of participants used the levels of reading cognitive processes differently could not be drawn. The findings, therefore, lead us to the fact that both groups in the study may use the same level of reading cognitive processes. Interestingly, the findings for hypotheses two and three are in line with the study carried out by McCray and Brunfaut (2018). Of course, it is worth mentioning that in the second hypothesis, at C1 level there was a slightly significant difference between the two groups which shows that this level of reading may be effective in making test-takers use different levels of reading cognitive processes.

For the last hypothesis of the study dealing with the point that higher-performing test-takers switch their gaze less between the word bank and the main text compared to lower performing test-takers, the findings showed that there were significant differences between the two groups at B1 and C1 levels in terms of applying different levels of reading cognitive processes. To be more specific, the findings of the last hypothesis indicate that the lower performing test-takers are engaged more in lower-level reading cognitive processes. This can be justified by the fact that, according to McCray and Brunfaut (2018), having more transition from text to the word bank by lower performing test-takers shows a possible explanation that the disruptions happen more in the 'linear' reading processes. To be more specific, when a bottom-up cognitive process in reading is hypothesized, words are being parsed into proposition units, proposition units form a mental model of the text, and so on, disruption to this process shows an increased likelihood for more of the processing to happen at the lower-levels of reading cognitive process.

The final word draws attention to task designing of banked gap-filling items. The results of this study revealed that the bank of words in gap-filling reading is the main challenge of the task that must be scrutinized. This is due to the fact that lower-performance participants of the present study made more visits to the bank of words in order to complete the task. Accordingly, this part of the task can remarkably affect the performance of test-takers in terms of using different cognitive processes. Furthermore, the findings of the study suggested

that the B1 level cannot differentiate between the test-takers in order to apply different reading cognitive processes and to implement the banked gap-filling tasks—and mostly assesses more local and lower-level reading processes. C1 level readings can make a difference between all test-takers to assess the ability of reading skills to make them use different reading cognitive processes both in lower-level and higher-level reading processing. In other words, for taking the optimized capability of the banked gap-filling tests, the task designers are advised to prefer C1 and C2 levels of reading comprehension tests in order to be sure that the construct of banked gap-filling tasks can make a proper distinction between higher performance test-takers and lower performance test-takers in terms of using different reading cognitive processes. To be more specific, C1 and C2 levels can measure more global reading skills (e.g., inferencing, and building a mental model of a text) and B1 measures much lower-level reading processing.

6. Conclusion

The present study attempted to investigate the cognitive processes EFL learners apply in order to implement the banked gap-filling tasks. To this end, a group of variables, both dependent and independent ones were included in the study. The dependent variables were eye movements of the participants including fixation, regressions, and saccade, and the independent variables were the levels of the participants and the difficulty levels of readings that appeared at B1 and C1 levels.

In order to analyze the cognitive processes being applied by the test-takers, the researchers collected the data through eye-tracking devices and stimulated recall interviews. The findings of the current study revealed that there was no significant difference between the high performers and low performers in terms of using different levels of reading cognitive processes at B1 level while there was a slightly significant difference between the two groups of participants in terms of applying reading cognitive processes at C1 level.

It can be concluded that the bank gap-filling tasks at B1 level cannot account for making distinctions between test-takers to use different reading cognitive processes. To be more specific, at B1 level, both higher performance test-takers and lower performance test-takers mostly applied lower-level reading cognitive processes to complete the task. Based on the findings of the present study at C1 level, there was a difference between two groups of the participants in terms of using reading cognitive processes. Accordingly, banked gap-filling reading tasks favor C1 and higher level students as the difficulty of reading texts can assess higher-level reading processes such as inference and building a mental model of the text.

Authors' Statement

Both authors worked together on the project and the paper. Hossein Karami supervised the project. Hamid Reza Mirzabagheri conducted the research and collected the data.

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References

- Alderson, J. C. (2000). *Assessing reading*. Cambridge University Press.
- Alderson, J. C., & Cseresznyés, M. (2003). *Into Europe: Reading and use of English*. TelekiLoszlo Foundation.
- Bax, S. (2013). The cognitive processing of candidates during reading tests: Evidence from eye tracking. *Language Testing, 30*(4), 441-465.
- Bax, S., & Weir, C. J. (2012). Investigating learners' cognitive processes during a computer-based CAE reading text. *Research Notes, 47*, 3-14.
- Bowles, M. E. (2010). *The think-aloud controversy in second language research*. Routledge.
- Brown, J. D. (2003). Twenty-five years of cloze testing research: So what? In G. Poedjosoedarmo (Ed.), *Teaching and assessing language proficiency* (pp. 79-111). SEAMEO Regional Language Centre.
- Brunfaut, T., & McCray, G. (2015). Looking into test-takers' cognitive processes whilst completing reading tasks: a mixed-method eye-tracking and stimulated recall study. (*ARAGsResearch Reports Online*; Vol. AR/2015/001). The British Council.
- Davies, A., Brown, A., Elder, C., Hill, K., Lumley, T., & McNamara, T. (1999). *Dictionary of language testing*. Cambridge University Press.

- Ericsson, K. A. (1988). Concurrent verbal reports on text comprehension: A review. *Text, 8*(4), 295-325.
- Ericsson, K. A., & Simon, H. A. (1993). *Protocol analysis: Verbal reports as data*. MIT Press.
- Gao, X., & Gu, X. (2008). An introspective study on test-taking process for banked cloze. *CELEA Journal, 31*(4), 3-16.
- Godfroid, A., & Uggen, M. S. (2013). Attention to irregular verbs by beginning learners of German: An eye-movement study. *Studies in Second Language Acquisition, 35*(2), 291-322
- Godfroid, A., Winke, P., & Rebuschat, P. (2015). Investigating implicit and explicit processing using L2 learners' eye-movement data. In P. Rebuschat (Ed.), *Implicit and Explicit Learning of Languages* (pp. 48-325).
- Grabe, W., & Stoller, F. (2011). *Teaching and researching reading* (2nd ed.). Longman.
- Graesser, A. C., Millis, K. K., & Zwaan, R. A. (1997). Discourse comprehension. *Annual Review of Psychology, 48*, 163-189.
- Graesser, A. C., Singer, M., & Trabasso, T. (1994). Constructing inferences during narrative text comprehension. *Psychological Review, 101*, 371-395.
- Holmqvist, K., Nyström, M., Anderson, R., Dewhurst, R., Jarodzka, H., & Van de Weijer, J. (2011). *Eye tracking: A comprehensive guide to methods and measures*. Oxford University Press.
- Khalifa, H., & Weir, C. J. (2009). *Examining reading: Research and practice in assessing second language reading*. Cambridge University Press.
- Kintsch, W. (1998). *Comprehension: A paradigm for cognition*. Cambridge University Press.
- Kintsch, W., & Rawson, K. A. (2005). Comprehension. In M. J. Snowling & C. Hulme (Eds.), *The science of reading: A handbook*, (pp. 209-226). Blackwell Publishing.

- McCray, G. Brunfaut, T. (2018). Investigating the construct measured by banked gap-fill items: Evidence from eye-tracking. *Language Testing*, 35(1) 51-73.
- McNamara, D. S., & Magliano, J. (2009). Toward a comprehensive model of comprehension. In B. Ross (Ed.), *The psychology of learning and motivation* (Vol. 51, pp. 297-384). Elsevier Science.
- Perfetti, C. (2007). Reading ability: Lexical quality to comprehension. *Scientific Studies of Reading*, 11(4), 357-383.
- Pressley, M., & Afflerbach, P. (1995). *Verbal protocols of reading: The nature of constructively responsive reading*. Erlbaum.
- Rayner, K. (1998). Eye movements in reading and information processing: 20 years of research. *Psychological Bulletin*, 124(3), 372-422.
- Rayner, K. (2009). Eye movements in reading: Models and data. *Journal of Eye Movement Research*, 2(5), 1-10.
- Reichle, E, Warren, T., & McConnell, K. (2009). Using E-Z reader to model the effects of higher-level language processing on eye movements during reading. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*, 16(1), 1-20.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2003). Text-familiarity, reading tasks and ESP test performance: A study on Iranian LEP and Non-LEP university students. *The Reading Matrix*, 3(1), online.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2007). Is text cohesion a precursor to reading success? *Journal of Educational Technology*, 3(4), 87-91.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2020a). English for Specific Purposes: Traditions, trends, directions. *Studies in English Language and Education*, 7(1), 247-268. <https://doi.org/10.24815/siele.v7i1.16342>
- Sasaki, M. (2000). Effects of cultural schemata on students' test-taking processes for cloze tests: A multiple data source approach. *Language Testing*, 17(1), 229-255.
- Schmitt, N. (2010). *An introduction to applied linguistics* (2nd ed.). Hodder Education, An Hachette UK Company.

- Sternberg, R. J., & Sternberg, K. (2012). *Cognitive psychology* (6th ed.). Cengage Learning.
- Taylor, K. L., & Dionne, J. P. (2000). Accessing problem-solving strategy knowledge: The complementary use of concurrent verbal protocols and retrospective debriefing. *Journal of Educational Psychology, 92*, 413-435.
- Van den Broek, P., Lorch, R. F., Jr., Linderholm, T., & Gustafson, M. (2001). The effects of readers' goals on the generation of inferences. *Memory & Cognition, 29*, 1081-1087.
- Verhoeven, L. & Perfetti, C. (2008). Advances in text comprehension: Model, process, and development. *Applied Cognitive Psychology, 22*, 293-301.
- Yamashita, J. (2003). Processes of taking a gap-filling test: Comparison of skilled and less skilled EFL readers. *Language Testing, 20*(3), 267-293.
- Zwaan, R. A., & Brown, C. M. (1996). The influence of language proficiency and comprehension skill on situation-model construction. *Discourse Processes, 21*, 289-327.
- Zwaan, R. A., & Singer, M. (2003). Text comprehension. In A. C. Graesser, M. A. Gernsbacher & S. R. Goldman (Eds.), *Handbook of discourse processes* (pp. 83-121). Routledge.